

Task event annotation using software ATLAS

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Abstract—Data annotation is the process of labeling data using human activity to tag the content. The video annotation tool used in the present work was the Software ATLAS, a graphical tool for annotating multimodal data flows. The hypothesis of the present work is that it is possible to annotate the task events of a data collection using video and signal track synchronized. The aim of this study is to elucidate the steps to complete the task event annotation process using software ATLAS. The validation of the proposed method was carried out using inertial sensors and video recordings. The biomedical signals included were the signals from accelerometer and gyroscope during gait. Data collection was filmed with a cellphone camera so that the physical mobility tasks could be watched by researchers to discriminate the task events. The task events were manually annotated, the inertial signal for each task event was labeled with initial and final time. Data video annotation as proposed here could be used as a tool to properly interpret the results and understand possible inconsistencies that may arise during the data analysis process and to understand the biological system responsible for generating the signals. Results show that the authors were able to annotate the task events of a data collection using the software ATLAS. The seven steps carried out to complete the task event annotation process are elucidated in the present study.

Keywords — *Signal processing, data annotation, gait mobility task, video annotation, ATLAS.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Healthcare is a dynamic industry that implements the latest technologies and instruments to track and analyze information about patients, hospitals, and other medical systems. The developments in biotechnologies, health care systems, and computing have led to a dramatic growth in the volume and variety of data about people's health and biology [1].

The purpose of data collection is to generate objective measures that are generalizable to a larger population. Previously, data collection took place through questionnaires with pre-determined response categories, medical records or medical documents [2]. Nowadays, several technological advancements have occurred to aid in obtaining more precise information from the individual, including the addition of quantitative measures for biological systems using various types of signal processing methods and sensors [3]. There are significant opportunities for using data to improve medical practice, characterize the individual's features using the model centered in the patient, produce more efficient information and services, generates new knowledge and drives innovation [1].

In this sense, data collection tools help to get a clearer picture of a patient's health, manage information quickly and

share it with other researchers. The first step in any signal processing is to understand the biological system responsible for generating the signals. Without this, it will not be possible to properly interpret the results and understand possible inconsistencies that may arise during the data analysis process [3], [4]. Biological systems are responsible for producing biomedical signals that reflect the state of the system. Examples of biomedical signals are electro-oculogram (EOG), accelerometry (Acc), mechanomyography (MMG), body temperature (TEMP), voice signals, the angular velocity of a limb during a movement (Gyr), electromyography (EMG), and electrocardiogram (ECG) [3].

Data annotation is the process of labeling data using human activity to tag the content in various formats such as video, images, or text [5]. Each data form has its own labeling procedure, the most common types are image, video, text, audio, and semantic annotation. The present study focusses on video annotation. Video annotation uses techniques such as bounding boxes to recognize motion frame-by-frame or using a video annotation tool, which is the method chosen for this work [5]. The video annotation tool used is the Software ATLAS [6]. ATLAS is a graphical tool for annotating multimodal data flows. In a human-machine interaction scenario, in addition to multichannel audio and video inputs, various biophysiological data can be recorded. This allows viewing on the same screen one or more videos together with the collected signal (biomedical signal) in a synchronized way, showing a marker that slides through the signal simultaneously with the video display. So that the synchronization of the video with the collected signal can happen [6]. A previous work containing the information for installation and use of the Software ATLAS is available on Zenodo [7].

Data is a valuable resource that may be re-used, linked, combined, and analyzed indefinitely, for a variety of purposes in healthcare. Collecting data and effectively managing information can be key to patient engagement and care. Advances in data science mean that there are now also more ways to collect, manage, link, and analyze health and biological data in order to generate information for research [1]. Labeled datasets led to accurate results, because they allow machines to understand and process the input patterns and use them to generate predictions. Therefore, the hypothesis of the present work is that it is possible to annotate the task events of a data collection using video and signal track synchronized. The aim of this study is to elucidate the steps to complete the task event annotation process using software ATLAS.

II. METHODS

The validation of the proposed method was carried out using inertial sensors and video recordings. The biomedical signals included are the signals from accelerometer and gyroscope, which measure the acceleration and angular velocity, respectively. In the present work, three wireless inertial sensors were used, two arranged in the pelvis, over the two ends of the iliac spine and one on the leg, over the fibula.

A video camera was used as an environment sensor. Several studies film the collections of data since videotaping is very useful to assess movement [9]. Therefore, the environment where the data collection took place had a positioned camera to capture all the pathway.

The technology available in smartphones allows high quality video recordings. Therefore, the data collection was filmed with a cellphone camera so that the physical mobility tasks could be watched by researchers to discriminate the task events during a physical mobility gait task [10], [11]. Table 1 shows the task events that were manually annotated.

TABLE 1: TASK EVENTS OF THE GAIT THAT WERE ANNOTATED AND THEIR RESPECTIVE DESCRIPTION.

Task Events	Description
Stand up	To stand up from a chair
Gait initiation	The time taken for the volunteer to complete the first step, which is the first two contacts of the foot with the floor.
First open gait	To walk 3 meters between the chair and the door.
First pass through a narrow door	The time taken for the volunteer to walk through the door, which is 30 cm before and 30 cm after the doorway.
First turn	To contour the obstacle 1.
Second turn	To contour the obstacle 2.
Third turn	To contour the obstacle 1 again.
Second pass through a narrow door	The time taken for the volunteer to walk through the door for the second time.
Second open gait	To walk 3 meters between the door and the chair.
Fourth turn	To turn in place to be at the position able to sit in the chair.
Sit	To sit in the chair

The presentation, visualization, statistical tests, and data analysis were conducted using RStudio, a software that generates good visualization graphs using the 'dygraph' function and allows the understanding of the signal characteristics. RStudio provides free and open-source tools for R and professional software ready for development work at scale [8].

The task events were manually annotated on ATLAS, the inertial signal (accelerometer and gyroscope in x, y, z axes) for each task event was labeled with initial and final time, this

is possible because the researcher watches the video recordings and the inertial signal in a synchronized form using the software ATLAS.

To help the synchronization process, the researcher created a pulse in the video recording, a light appears when the data collection with the inertial sensor starts. By pressing the light button simultaneously with the sensor's button. The video, therefore, needed to be cut according to the trials measured using the inertial sensors. The process of cutting the video was conducted using the software Wondershare Filmora. Wondershare Filmora provides free tools to create and edit videos with advanced features like keyframing and motion tracking.

III. RESULTS

Figures 1 and 2 show ATLAS software screen with the video synchronized with the accelerometer and gyroscope in x axis for the sensor placed on the left end of the iliac spine (S2AX and S2GX) and the label of the task events (TASK_EVENT) with eleven labeled tasks, the eleven tasks shown in Table 1. in Figure 2, the volunteer is performing the open gait task event, to walk 3 meters between the chair and the door for the first time.

Fig. 1. ATLAS screen with the video synchronized with the accelerometer and gyroscope in x axis for the sensor placed on the left end of the iliac spine (S2AX and S2GX) and the label of the task events (TASK_EVENT).

Fig. 2. ATLAS screen shows the blue cursor on the third task event, which means the first open gait, on the video the volunteer is walking from the chair to the doorway.

Figures 3 to Figure 9 represent the flow diagrams of the seven steps to complete the task event annotation process using software ATLAS.

Fig. 3. Flow diagram presenting the Step 1, to compress videos and organize sensors files for each trial.

Fig. 4. Flow diagram presenting the Step 2, to separate video by trial using Wondershare Filmora software.

Fig. 5. Flow diagram presenting the Step 3, to create a project on ATLAS and fill datatrack folder.

Fig. 6. Flow diagram presenting the Step 4, to add biomedical signal and video recording of data collection.

STEP 5 - ADD ANNOTATION LABELS - TASK EVENTS

Fig. 7. Flow diagram presenting the Step 5, add annotation labels with the name of each task event on ATLAS.

STEP 6 - VIDEO ANNOTATION

Fig. 8. Flow diagram presenting the Step 6, annotate initial and final task for each task event.

Three sensors were used in the data collection, and only one sensor is synchronized with the pulse as a light in the videorecording. The pulse used in the data collection was a light that would be trigger by the researcher responsible for the data collection, by pressing the light button simultaneously with the sensor's button. So, the last step, to cut the sensors signal, represents the effort to make the three sensors signals have the same initial movement time, to stand up from the chair.

Results show that the gait task used as a physical mobility task was capable to create waveforms that could be discriminated. The task events - (1) stand up; (2) gait initiation; (3) first open gait; (4) first pass through a narrow door; (5) first turn; (6) second turn; (7) third turn; (8) second pass through a narrow door; (9) second open gait; (10) fourth turn; and (11) sit - could be manually annotated. This experiment shows that it is possible to annotate the task events of a data collection using video and signal track synchronized. The authors were able to elucidate the steps to complete the task event annotation process using software ATLAS.

STEP 7 - CUT THE SENSORS SIGNAL

Fig. 9. Flow diagram presenting the Step 7, to cut the sensor signals using RStudio.

IV. DISCUSSION

The purposes, procedures, and benefits of quantitative evaluation of biological systems are well known and accepted by the academic community [2]. Data video annotation as proposed here could be used as a tool to properly interpret the results and understand possible inconsistencies that may arise during the data analysis process and to understand the biological system responsible for generating the signals. The inertial signals and the video recording with smartphone camera were used as input for the video annotation software presented in this study. This allowed the researchers to annotate the task events of a data collection. As a result, the authors were capable to elucidate the seven steps to complete the task event annotation process using software ATLAS.

Figure 3 shows the step 1, to compress videos and organize sensors files for each trial. Video compressing is important because depending on the volume of information, processing may be slower, so it is advantageous to compress the video before inserting it into the program. It is possible to download a video compressor app for Android and iOS.

Figure 4 presents the step 2, to separate video by trial using Wondershare Filmora software. The pulse as a light in the video recordings by pressing the light button simultaneously with the sensor's button was very helpful to complete this step.

Figure 5 have the diagram flow of step 3, the creation a project on ATLAS and fill datatrack folder. In this step, it is important to plot the signal on RStudio and annotate the time for the initial movement, to stand up from a chair, for the three sensors (two on the end of iliac spine and one on the leg) and

highlight the shortest time, which is the sensor that was pressed together with the light button. This will be the inertial signal to be synchronized initially with the video on ATLAS. The steps from 1 to 4 are very important to prepare the data for the analysis on ATLAS.

Figure 6 presents the step 4, to add biomedical signal and video recording of data collection. This step shows how to add the biomedical signal and the video on the ATLAS project. The light pulse is crucial to cut the compressed video using software Wondershare Filmora, however, it is important for the researcher to verify if the synchronism of both signal and video is correct, otherwise, changes can be done using the edit video software.

Figure 7 shows step 5, to add annotation labels with the name of each task event on ATLAS. This step shows where to press in ATLAS software to add a label and star the annotation data process. It is important to rename the labels with the respective task event. Figure 8 represents step 6, to annotate initial and final task for each task event on ATLAS by simply clicking and dragging the label to the events' initial and final time.

Figure 9 shows step 7, to cut the sensor signals using RStudio, the step that allows the annotation of each task event to be used in all collected signals. As disclosed before, three sensors were used in the data collection, and only one sensor is synchronized with the pulse as a light in the videorecording. Therefore, for the information of video annotation data from step 1 to step 6 to be consider for the other two sensors that were not synchronized with the video, the step 7, in which the original data is subset, results in all three sensors signals with the same initial movement time, to stand up from the chair.

Schaafsma et al. [11] also videotaped a gait task, and the video analysis was made by three observers, who independently watched the tasks videotapes and elucidate the number of a gait disturbance episode called freezing of gait. The researchers clarify that using exclusively the video rating method, they might have missed the annotation for very brief gait specific episodes [12]. In the study of Popovic et al. [13], the gait analysis was carried out from three sources, videotapes, ground reaction forces and accelerations.

The conclusion is that for an efficient data collection, the correct methods of organization, processing, storage, and analysis are crucial. The first and most important stage of a research is to choose methods that meet the needs and aims for the work, considering which information should be collected and the instruments needed.

There are a lot of opportunities of data use as it has become a strong public interest in the responsible use of data to support the development of knowledge and innovation through scientific research concerning healthcare. These innovations aim to improve the wellbeing of all through improved health advice, treatment, and care. The convenience offered by data annotation from biomedical signals include getting a clearer picture of a patient's health, manage information quickly, share it with other researcher, understand the biological system responsible for generating the signals, and interpreting the results during the data analysis process. This builds a stronger evidence base to predict, prevent, and treat disease, helping the development of new treatments or personalized treatments and care, according to the individuals need.

The system presented in this work was tested in a controlled study with subjects and it has shown satisfactory results. It composes a doctoral thesis that is still in progress. The limitation of the study is the time spent to carry out the seven steps in a large data collection.

V. CONCLUSION

It is very important that the Biomedical Engineer understands the main biomedical systems and signals so that he or she can fully exercise the profession, ATLAS software proved to be an efficient tool to help the signal visualization and its comprehension. Results show that the authors were able to annotate the task events of a data collection accessing videos and the signals collected using inertial sensors in a synchronized way on ATLAS.

The seven steps carried out to complete the task event annotation process are elucidated in the present study, as well as a manual explaining how to install and use the software ATLAS.

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